

WAYS TO EFFECTIVELY USE RESOURCES IN THE SERVICE SECTOR

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Аннотасия: В статье исследуя способы эффективного использования ресурсов на предприятиях сферы услуг, источники и факторы повышения эффективности услуг, оценка ее взаимосвязи с производительностью при анализе эффективности, развитие отраслей сферы услуг, динамика экономического роста в отраслях и особенности эффективного развития сферы услуг.

Ключевые слова: сфера услуг, просесс обслуживания, эффективность, производительност труда, экономический рост, основные фонды, части, внутренние факторы, внешние факторы, потребители.

Annotation: In the article is investigated the ways of efficient use of resources in service enterprises, sources and factors of services efficiency, assessing its effective strength in order to analyze productivity, development of service sectors, the dynamics of economic growth in the sector and the specifics of service sector effective development.

Key words: branch of the service, the process of service, effectiveness, productivity of labor, economic growth, basic funds, parts, internal factors, external factors, consumers.

Introduction.

Today, in the digital economy, the importance of the service sector is growing. In service enterprises, it is possible to have a positive impact on economic growth rates by effectively using resources, improving service quality and productivity. Rational use of resources, ensuring the efficiency of the service process and increasing labor productivity play an important role in the sustainable development of the national economy. This article analyzes methods for effectively using resources in service industries, factors for improving service efficiency, and the dynamics of economic development of service industries.

Main part.

In the context of the development of the digital economy, it is important to study the sources and factors of increasing the efficiency of production (service provision) as a means of determining the rational use of resources by service enterprises. Currently, economic reforms should be aimed at the effective

development of the national economy. In this regard, the effective development of the service sector implies improving the quality of services provided to the population and fully satisfying their various requirements. The reforms being implemented in our republic should be aimed at increasing the efficiency of the national economy. The development of the service sector, which is considered a component of it, is one of the important directions for improving the quality of services to the population and satisfying their various requirements. In analyzing the efficiency of service enterprises, an important role is played by assessing its relationship with productivity, in which productivity is an indicator that determines the quantitative approach to determining overall efficiency. The expansion of service sectors also affects the change in the structure of the gross domestic product of developed countries. Today, the main criterion for including a particular country in the list of developed countries is that the share of the service sector in its gross domestic product is higher than 65-70 percent. At the current stage of the development of the economy of our republic, the requirements for the quantity and quality of service services are increasing. This makes it necessary to identify the factors of economic growth in the service sector and achieve economic efficiency. Also, increasing the position and competitiveness of service enterprises in national and international markets and increasing the volume of their exports due to improving the quality of services are important factors in achieving economic growth in the sector.

In the analysis of efficiency in enterprises, an important role is played by assessing its relationship with productivity, in which productivity is an indicator that determines the quantitative approach to determining overall efficiency. In service enterprises, indicators of gross product and the number of employed people are used to determine labor productivity in a single sector. The new concept of labor productivity today is based on reducing costs, effective and permanent opportunities that expand over time, not only the savings of economic resources, but also qualitative changes in the self-development of a person participating in the consumption process. The implementation of this concept is graded according to the importance of production. It requires a focus on prospective social needs. Increasing labor productivity, along with determining the dynamics of gross domestic product, meets the principles of reducing production costs and thus serves as a criterion for the final results of the management process in a market economy. Macroeconomic indicators of labor productivity growth in the service sector make it possible to monitor the

balance of social and economic development and their compliance with market equilibrium conditions.

When calculating labor productivity in service sectors, the ratio of the volume of gross product created in the sector to the total number of people employed in the sector is determined.

$$MU_t = YM / B$$

where: MU_t is the labor productivity indicator in the service sector,

YM is the gross product created in the sector,

B is the number of jobs in the sector.

The introduction of this indicator for determining labor productivity in service sectors is based on the following:

1. The use of in-kind indicators of the development of services in several types of activity in the service sector complicates the process of calculating productivity. 2. In accordance with the principles of the system of national accounts of our republic, there is no specific relationship between indicators such as costs per employee and the volume of production (services) for statistics. The relationship between these indicators can be determined in specific sectors of material production. In the main sectors of the service sector, the volume of gross product is determined on the basis of labor costs and represents the relationship between gross value added and labor costs. Accordingly, economic efficiency is often close to zero. Sometimes there is a possibility that it will be below zero. Therefore, when calculating labor productivity in service enterprises, statistics of employees working in the sector are used. 3. In order to compare statistical data in the sector presented with statistical indicators in other sectors of the economy, it is necessary to carry out a single method and a single statistical assessment. In this case, the value of services produced, the average number of employees, the value of fixed assets are formed at different levels and in different sectors. Since the gross value added (GVA) indicator in the service sector is a valuable indicator, we used the deflator (comparison) method, that is, we express the volume of gross value added in a comparative form. Deflators (comparison indices) are used to compare value indicators. The service process is the activity of the service provider in interaction with the consumer. The service process is provided by the economic resources of the enterprises of the sector.

The service process includes the analysis of consumer orders, the development of projects, that is, the procedure and conditions for the implementation of organizational and technical tasks and the implementation of

the service process, improving the quality of services and their delivery to consumers. In the conditions of innovative development of the economy, industry specialists working in our republic must have a high level of professional knowledge and qualification requirements for all features of the service process. This ensures the achievement of service efficiency and improvement of service quality in service enterprises by increasing the efficiency of using economic resources. The quality of services often depends on the methods of service production. The methods of service provision depend on the types and specialization of service enterprises and organizations. Working conditions directly affect the quality of service, and in this process they affect the consumer. The effectiveness of the service enterprise depends on the scientific organization of the organizational-managerial and organizational-economic processes of the enterprise managers. The organizational-managerial activities of the service enterprise include the following:

- planning the activities of the service enterprise, determining the prospects for the development of the enterprise as a result of changes in the conditions of the service market or the range of services;
- assessing production and non-production costs;
- optimizing the composition of technological equipment and technical means, taking into account the range and quality level of services;
- selecting specialists with socio-psychological competence to work with consumers;
- improving the professional skills and qualification level of service employees;
- ensuring intensive development by increasing labor productivity;
- technical equipment of the production process and service activities;
- assessing the effectiveness of production and service costs;
- improving service results.

Conclusion.

Efficient use of resources in the service sector is an important factor in improving the quality of services, increasing economic efficiency and ensuring competitiveness. By increasing labor productivity and optimizing service processes, the position of service enterprises in domestic and foreign markets is strengthened. To achieve economic growth in the service sector, it is necessary to organize the service process, constantly work on the types and quality of services. Sustainable growth of the national economy can be ensured by developing service industries and introducing digital innovations.

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